

Zenodo User Guide

UPLOADING PUBLICATIONS AND DELIVERABLES

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Uploading Publications and Deliverables to Zenodo

Zenodo is an open access repository developed by the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit datasets, research software, reports, deliverables and publications, which in turn facilitates the ease of access of this information to the wider scientific community. Open access data systems must ensure that data follow the FAIR principles, thus data are **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable which promotes the maximum use of research data. When data are open access it promotes collaborations and reduces duplication of work, which are also important aims in the One Health EJP.

The One Health EJP requires its scientific outcomes to be publicly available where possible, and as soon as possible.

Please carefully read the metadata requirements when uploading public deliverables and publications.

For any technical support, please contact ohajp@sciensano.be

Here is a step by step guide to uploading a document to Zenodo.

1. Log in to Zenodo

Step 1: Visit <https://zenodo.org>

Step 2: Create an account (by clicking on “Sign up”) or log in to your existing account (by clicking on “Log in”).

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. On the right side of the navigation bar, there are 'Log in' and 'Sign up' buttons. Below the navigation bar, the 'Featured communities' section is visible, featuring the 'National COVID Cohort Collaborative (N3C)' with a description and a 'New upload' button. The 'Recent uploads' section shows a document titled 'The Pan-SL-CoV/GD sequences may be from contamination.' by Daoyu Zhang, with a 'View' button. On the right side, there is a 'Need help?' section with a 'Contact us' button and a list of services provided.

2. “Upload” sections

Step 1: Click “Upload”

The screenshot shows the Zenodo website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and buttons for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. The 'Upload' button is highlighted with a blue rectangular box. Below the navigation bar, there is a section for 'Featured communities' featuring the 'Coronavirus Disease Research Community - COVID-19'. To the right of this community card, there are 'Browse' and 'New upload' buttons. The 'New upload' button is not highlighted in this step.

Step 2: Click “New Upload”. The upload page appears.

This screenshot is identical to the previous one, but the 'New upload' button in the 'Featured communities' section is now highlighted with a blue rectangular box, indicating the next step in the process.

On the upload page, the following sections appear:

- Files
- Communities
- Upload type
- Basic information
- License
- Funding

You should fill them as indicated below.

3. Upload a document to Zenodo

3.1. "Files" section

This section serves to upload the document to the system.

Step 1: Upload your file by clicking on "Choose files" then selecting on your computer the file to be uploaded.

Step 2: Once your file appears under "Filename", click "Start upload". (please note that it is impossible to publish the document if you have not clicked on "Start upload" before).

Filename (1 files)	Size	Progress	Delete
Air_Sample Case Study v4.pdf 11d5.6696b74f68d66b02e7011a663e9b340a8	594 Kb	✓	

Note: File addition, removal or modification are not allowed after you have published your upload. This is because a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is registered with [DataCite](#) for each upload.
(minimum 1 file required, max 50 GB per dataset - contact us for larger datasets)

3.2. “Communities” section

This section serves to select the community under which you intend to upload the document (in this case it is One Health EJP).

Step 1: Scroll down to “Communities” and type “OHEJP” and click on “One Health EJP”. Your upload will be added to the One Health EJP Community

Instructions: (i) Upload minimum one file or fill-in required fields (marked with a red star). (ii) Press “Save” to save your upload for editing later. (iii) When ready, press “Publish” to finalize and make your upload public.

Filename (1 files)	Size	Progress	Delete
Air Sample Case Study v4.pdf	594 Kb		

Note: File addition, removal or modification are not allowed after you have published your upload. This is because a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is registered with [DataCite](#) for each upload.
(minimum 1 file required, max 50 GB per dataset - contact us for larger datasets)

Communities recommended

OHEJP

One Health EJP
The One Health European Joint Program (OHEJP) aims at integrating the complementary expertise of partners across Europe in order to prepare common action against infectious health...

3.3. “Upload type” section

This section serves to describe the type of upload: journal article, project deliverable, etc.

Step 1: If the document to upload is a Journal article or a project deliverable, select “Publication”.

Upload type required

Publication Poster Presentation Dataset Image Video/Audio Software Lesson Physical object Other

Step 2 : a list appears under publication type (“Journal article” or “Project deliverable”).

NB: in step 1 and step 2 we have presented the main OHEJP documents types (“Journal article” and “Project deliverable”). Other options may be chosen if needed (“Poster”, “Presentation”, “Other”, etc.).

Upload type required ▾

Publication
 Poster
 Presentation
 Dataset
 Image
 Video/Audio
 Software
 Lesson
 Physical object
 Other

Publication type
 Journal article
 Annotation collection
 Book
 Book section
 Conference paper
 Data management plan
Journal article
 Patent
 Preprint
 Project deliverable
 Project milestone
 Proposal
 Report
 Software documentation
 Taxonomic treatment
 Technical note
 Thesis
 Working paper
 Other

Basic information

Digital Object Identifier

Publication date *

3.4. “Basic information” section

In this section identification, titles and keywords are required.

Step 1 : If the document already has a DOI, please copy it and paste it in the “Digital Object Identifier” section. Otherwise, leave empty.

Basic information required ▾

Digital Object Identifier

Optional. Did your publisher already assign a DOI to your upload? If not, leave the field empty and we will register a new DOI for you. A DOI allows others to easily and unambiguously cite your upload. Please note that it is NOT possible to edit a Zenodo DOI once it has been registered by us, while it is always possible to edit a custom DOI.

Step 2: Fill in the publication date.

Publication date *

Required. Format: YYYY-MM-DD. In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of first publication.

Step 3: If the document to upload is a publication, provide the official title.

If the document to upload is a deliverable, enter the deliverable number and the full title (e.g. “Deliverable D-JRP-TOXOSOURCES-WP3.2 SOP on detection of *T. gondii* in selected fresh produce matrix” or “D-JRP8-4.2 Overview of Metastava output”).

Title *

Required.

Step 4: Enter the Author(s) name(s)

Authors *

Optional.

Step 5: Under “**Description**”: enter the name of the project that the publication relates to, for example: “**JRP-TOXOSOURCES**” or “**OHEJP Project: COHESIVE** “. This can be followed by a brief description of the document.

Description *

B I S x₂ x²
[Link] [Image] [List] [Table] [Quote] [Undo] [Redo] [Source] [Refresh]

OHEJP Project: COHESIVE

Required.

Step 6: Under “**Keywords**”: enter the One Health EJP project name (ex: Listadapt, MedVetKlebs...) and any other main keywords relevant for the document. The keywords are important metadata that help to make the document findable (the first point of FAIR-principle).

Keywords

⇅ ×

Enter the first keyword in the empty field.

Keywords

Listadapt

⇅ ×

+ Add another keyword

If you need to add a new keyword: click on “**+Add another keyword**”. A new empty field appears, in which you can type the second keyword. (Repeat as many times as needed).

Keywords

Listadapt

⇅ ×

WGS

⇅ ×

+ Add another keyword

3.5. “License” section

In this section, information about the access rights and the License type are required.

Step1: Select the Access right

- “**Open Access**”: by default (Gold open access, or Green open access after the end of the embargo)

- “**Embargoed Access**”: Green open access during the max. 6 month embargo period (if you choose this access type, you need to change it to “**Open Access**” at the end of the embargo period)
- “**Restricted Access**”: discouraged
- “**Closed Access**”: discouraged

License required ▾

Access right *

- Open Access
- Embargoed Access
- Restricted Access
- Closed Access

Required. Open access uploads have considerably higher visibility on Zenodo.

Step 2: Select the correct “**License**”.

For publications, make sure to select the License of the Scientific Journal corresponding with the publication).

The default License that Zenodo suggests is the “**Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**” (CC-BY-4.0), other options appear as drop down menu when you start writing the name of the license.

License *

Required. Selected license applies to all of your files displayed on the top of the form. If you want to upload some of your files under different licenses, please do so in separate uploads. If you cannot find the license you're looking for, include a relevant LICENSE file in your record and choose one of the *Other* licenses available (*Other (Open)*, *Other (Attribution)*, etc.). The supported licenses in the list are harvested from opendefinition.org and spdx.org. If you think that a license is missing from the list, please [contact us](#).

Zenodo has hundreds of license options in the database, and there is also option ‘Other’.
<https://blog.zenodo.org/2018/11/22/2018-11-22-new-licenses/>

3.6. “Funding” section

In this section the grant number is requested (for OHEJP: 773830).

Step 1: in the empty field, type “773830”

Funding recommended ▾

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](#). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants

Optional. OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding agencies, please use the “Other” option. Note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your uploads.

[+ Add another grant](#)

One Health EJP 773830

Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards.

Step 2: click on “**One Health EJP 773830**”

Funding recommended ▾

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](#). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants

Optional, OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding agencies, note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your uploads.

[+ Add another grant](#)

One Health EJP 773830

Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards.

3.7. Other sections

Complete any other relevant information if you wish.

Related/alternate identifiers	recommended ▾
Contributors	optional ▾
References	optional ▾
Journal	optional ▾
Conference	optional ▾
Book/Report/Chapter	optional ▾
Thesis	optional ▾
Subjects	optional ▾

4. Save and publish the document

Step 1: Finalise the upload by clicking “Save”.

References	optional ▾
Journal	optional ▾
Conference	optional ▾
Book/Report/Chapter	optional ▾
Thesis	optional ▾
Subjects	optional ▾

Delete
Save
Publish

Step 2: Click on “Publish”

Journal	optional >
Conference	optional >
Book/Report/Chapter	optional >
Thesis	optional >
Subjects	optional >

Step 3: The following message appears. Click on “I understand”.

Saved successfully

New upload

Instructions: (1) Upload minimum one file or file-in-repository

Files:

Filename (1 files)	Size	Progress	Delete
Test.docx md5:5fba977f52eb9efadc279c6014ef497b	13 kB	✓	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>

Note: File addition, removal or modification are not allowed after you have published your upload. This is because a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is registered with DataCite for each upload.
(minimum 1 file required, max 50 GB per dataset - contact us for larger datasets)
If you're experiencing issues with uploading larger files, read our FAQ section on file upload issues.

Warning

Once the record is published you will no longer be able to change the files in this upload. This is because a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be registered immediately after publishing. You will still be able to update the record's metadata later.

If you only want to create a test upload, please do so on Zenodo Sandbox.

5. Editing the document

The author of the document is the only person able to edit the document after it has been published.

Step 1: Click on your document.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for a document titled "Extensive antimicrobial resistance mobilization via multicopy plasmid encapsidation mediated by temperate phages". The document is dated November 4, 2020, and is categorized as a "Journal article" and "Open Access". The author information lists Lorena Rodríguez-Rubio, Carlos Serna, Manuel Ares-Arroyo, Bosco R Matamoros, Jose F Delgado-Bias, Natalia Montero, Cristina Bernabe-Baias, Emilia F Wedel, Irene S Mendez, Maitte Muniesa, and Bruno Gonzalez-Zorn. The document has 38 views and 26 downloads. It is indexed in OpenAIRE. The "Edit" button is visible in the top right corner of the document preview area.

Step 2: Click on "Edit"

This screenshot is identical to the previous one, but the "Edit" button in the top right corner of the document preview area is highlighted with a blue rectangular box, indicating the step to click on the document for editing.

Step 3: You can now make updates and then click on “Save”.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo 'Edit upload' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the Zenodo logo, a search bar, and links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. The user's email address 'racha.elmounaged@sciensano.be' is displayed in the top right. Below the navigation bar, there are two buttons: 'Discard changes' and 'Save'. The 'Save' button is highlighted with a blue box. Below the buttons, the page title is 'Edit upload'. There are instructions: '(i) Upload minimum one file or fill-in required fields (marked with a red star) (ii) Press "Save" to save your upload for editing later (iii) When ready, press "Publish" to finalize and make your upload public'. A table shows the upload details:

Filename (1 files)	Size	Progress	Delete
Extensive antimicrobial resistance mobilization vi ... md5:99c89dae5a33191f3e5a7a9a166cd171	580 kB	✓	

Below the table, there is a note: 'Note: File addition, removal or modification are not allowed after you have published your upload. This is because a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) is registered with DataCite for each upload. (minimum 1 file required, max 50 GB per dataset - contact us for larger datasets)'. If you're experiencing issues with uploading larger files, read our FAQ section on file upload issues. At the bottom, there is a 'Communities' section with a dropdown menu set to 'recommended'.

Step 4: Click on “Publish”.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo 'Edit upload' interface after a successful save. A green notification bar at the top says 'Saved successfully'. The 'Save' button is now disabled, and the 'Publish' button is highlighted with a blue box. The rest of the page content is identical to the previous screenshot, including the table with the upload details and the 'Communities' section.

6. Accepting the document in the OHEJP community

Please inform the Communications Team at OHEJPCommunications@surrey.ac.uk and send them the Zenodo URL of the upload. They will accept the submission in the OHEJP Community.

Once you have published the submission you will be able to view the upload. The URL can be found here:

zenodo.org/record/4647937#YXU7q6gzZM0

zenodo Search Upload Communities rachaelmounaged@sciensano.be

March 1, 2021 Journal article Open Access

Infection prevention and control practices of ambulatory veterinarians: A questionnaire study in Finland

Verkola, M.; Järvelä, T.; Järvinen, A.; Jokelainen, P.; Virtala, A.-M.; Kinnunen, P. M.; Heikinheimo, A.
Publication, JRP-TOXOSOURCES

19 views 18 downloads [See more details...](#)

Indexed in

Publication date: March 1, 2021
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Keyword(s): Infection prevention and control TOXOSOURCES
Grants:

Preview

Page: 1 of 12 Automatic Zoom

ORIGINAL ARTICLE WILEY

Infection prevention and control practices of ambulatory veterinarians: A questionnaire study in Finland

Maria Verkola, Taina Järvelä, Antti Järvinen, Pekka Jokelainen, Anniina Virtala, Petteri Kinnunen, and Anni Heikinheimo